

ELEKTR ZANJIRIDAGI TEBRANISHLAR

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada elektr zanjirdagi tebranishlarga doir misolning yechilish usuli to'liq yoritib berigan.

Kalit so'zlar: Qarshilik, sig'im, kondensator, induktivlik, rezonans.

Аннотация: В этой статье полностью объясняется метод решения на примере колебаний в электрической цепи.

Ключевые слова: Сопротивление, емкость, конденсатор, индуктивность, резонанс.

Abstract: In this article, the method of solving the example of oscillations in an electric circuit is fully explained.

Keywords: Resistance, capacitance, capacitor, inductance, resonance.

Elektr zanjiridagi tebranishlar.

Misol. Elektr yurituvchi kuchi $e(t)$ ga teng bo'lga manbaga ketma-ket ulangan L induktivlik g'altagi, R qarshilik va C sig'imdan iborat kontur ulangan. Agar boshlang'ich momentda konturdagi tok va kondensator zaryadi nolga teng bo'lsa, zanjirdagi I tokni t vaqtning funksiyasi kabi toping.(2-rasm)

2-rasm.

Yechilishi: Kirxgof qonuniga ko'ra zanjirdagi elektr yurituvchi kuch induktivlikdagi, qarshilikdagi va sig'imdagi kuchlanishlar pasayishi yig'indisiga teng:

$$e(t) = u_L + u_R + u_C$$

Ular I tok bilan quyidagi munosabatlar orqali bog'langan:

$$u_L = L \frac{di}{dt}, \quad u_R = Ri, \quad u_C = \frac{1}{C} \int_0^t i(\tau) d\tau.$$

Shunday qilib quyidagi tenglama hosil bo'ladi:

$$e(t) = L \frac{di}{dt} + Ri + \frac{1}{C} \int_0^t i(\tau) d\tau.$$

Bu integro-differensial tenglamadir, ya'ni tenglamalarning eng murakkab turlaridan bieiga mansubdir, biroq mazkur holda differensiallash orqali undan oddiy differensial tenglama o'tish mumkin. Xaqiqattan xam, t bo'yicha differensiallab, koeffitsentlari o'zgarmas bo'lgan ikkinchi tartibli chiziqli differensial tenglamani hosil qilamiz:

$$L \frac{d^2i}{dt^2} + R \frac{di}{dt} + \frac{1}{C} i = \frac{de}{dt} \quad (1)$$

Ikki holni qaraymiz.

1-hol. $E(t) = E = \text{const}$. Bu holda $\frac{de}{dt} = 0$ va (13) tenglama bir jinsli

$$\frac{d^2i}{dt^2} + \frac{R}{L} \frac{di}{dt} + \frac{1}{LC} i = 0 \quad (2)$$

Tenglamaga aylanadi. Bu tenglama erkin mexanikaviy tebranishlar (muhit qarshiligi hisobga olingandagi) tenglamasiga o'xshashdir, Uning $r^2 + \frac{R}{L}r + \frac{1}{LC} = 0$ xarakteristik tenglamasi

$$r_{1,2} = -\frac{R}{2L} \pm \sqrt{\frac{R^2}{4L^2} - \frac{1}{LC}} = -\frac{R}{2L} \pm \sqrt{\frac{R^2C - 4L}{4L^2C}}$$

Ildizlarga ega bo'ladi. Agar $R^2C - 4L \geq 0$ bo'lsa, xarakteristik tenglamaning ikkala ildizi haqiqiy va umumiy yechim nodavriy funksiya bo'ladi. Bunga mos ravishda tok xam nodavriy bo'ladi. $R^2C - 4L = 0$ bo'lgandagi kabi, zanjirda xech qanday elektr tebranishlari vujudga kelmaydi. Agar $R^2C - 4L < 0$ bo'lsa.

$$i = e^{-\delta t}(C_1 \cos \omega_1 t + C_2 \sin \omega_1 t).$$

(bu yerda $\delta = \frac{R}{2L}$, $\omega_1^2 = \frac{1}{LC} - \frac{R^2}{4L^2}$ deb olingan) umumiy yechim elektr tebranishlarni ifodalaydi.

$L \frac{di}{dt} \Big|_{t=0} = E$ ekanligini ko'rish oson, bu yerda $\frac{di}{dt} \Big|_{t=0} = \frac{E}{L}$ va shunday qilib, boshlang'ich shartlar quyidagicha yoziladi:

$$i|_{t=0} = 0, \quad \frac{di}{dt} \Big|_{t=0} = \frac{E}{L}.$$

I ni t bo'yicha differensiallab, topamiz:

$$\frac{di}{dt} = e^{-\delta t}(-\delta(C_1 \cos \omega_1 t + C_2 \sin \omega_1 t) + \omega_1(-C_1 \sin \omega_1 t + C_2 \cos \omega_1 t))$$

T=0 ni I va $\frac{di}{dt}$ ning ifodalariga qo'yib,

$$0 = C_1,$$

$$\frac{E}{L} = -\delta C_1 + \omega_1 C_2$$

Ni topamiz, bu yerda $C_1 = 0$ va $C_2 = \frac{E}{L\omega_1}$, natijada yechim ushbu ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$i = \frac{E}{L\omega_1} e^{-\delta t} \sin \omega_1 t.$$

2-hol . $e(t) = E\sin\omega t$. Bu holda $\frac{de}{dt} = E\omega\cos\omega t$. Quyidagi chiziqli bir jinsli bo'lmagan tenglama hosil bo'ladi:

$$L \frac{d^2i}{dt^2} + R \frac{di}{dt} + \frac{1}{C}i = E\omega\cos\omega t. \quad (3)$$

Bu bir jinsli bo'lmagan tenglamaga mos bir jinsli tenglama yuqorida ko'rilgan tenglamadan (1-hol) iborat bo'ladi, shuning uchun bir jinsli bo'lmagan tenglamaning hususiy yechimini topish qoladi. Uni

$$i = A\cos\omega t + B\sin\omega t$$

Shaklda izlash kerak. Aniqmas koeffitsentlarni topish uchun quyidagilarni hisoblaymiz:

$$\frac{1}{C}i = A\cos\omega t + B\sin\omega t$$

$$R|i' = -A\omega\sin\omega t + B\omega\cos\omega t$$

$$L|i'' = -A\omega^2\cos\omega t - B\omega^2\sin\omega t$$

Va A,B ga nisbatan algebraik tenglamalar sistemasiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\left(\frac{1}{C} - L\omega^2\right)A + \omega RB = E\omega, \quad -\omega RA + \left(\frac{1}{C} - L\omega^2\right)B = 0.$$

Bu sistemani yechib,

$$A = \frac{E\omega \left(\frac{1}{C} - L\omega^2\right)}{\left(\frac{1}{C} - L\omega^2\right)^2 + \omega^2 R^2}, \quad B = \frac{E\omega^2 R}{\left(\frac{1}{C} - L\omega^2\right)^2 + \omega^2 R^2}$$

Ni topamiz, koeffitsentlarning bu qiymatlarida hususiy yechim quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$\bar{i} = \frac{E\omega}{\left(\frac{1}{C} - L\omega^2\right)^2 + \omega^2 R^2} \left[\left(\frac{1}{C} - L\omega^2\right) \cos\omega t + \omega R \sin\omega t \right].$$

Bir jinsli bo'lmagan tenglamaning umumiy yechimi mos bir jinsli tenglamaning umumiy yechimi va bir jinsli bo'lmagan tenglamaning hususiy yechimi yig'indisidan iborat, ya'ni

$$i = I + \bar{i} = e^{-\delta t}(C_1 \cos \omega_1 t + C_2 \sin \omega_1 t) + \frac{E}{\left(\frac{1}{C} - L\omega^2\right)^2 + \omega^2 R^2} \left[\left(\frac{1}{C\omega} - L\omega\right) \cos \omega t + R \sin \omega t \right].$$

Belgilashlar kiritamiz: $L\omega - \frac{1}{C\omega} = X$; $\sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{C\omega} - L\omega\right)^2 + R^2} = \sqrt{R^2 + X^2} = Z$;

U holda

$$i = e^{-\delta t}(C_1 \cos \omega_1 t + C_2 \sin \omega_1 t) - \frac{E}{Z^2}(X \cos \omega t - R \sin \omega t).$$

C_1 va C_2 larni boshlang'ich shartlardan topamiz:

$$i|_{t=0} = 0, \quad \left. \frac{di}{dt} \right|_{t=0} = 0, \quad (\text{keying shart})$$

$$L \frac{di}{dt} + Ri + \frac{1}{C} \int_0^t i(\tau) d\tau = E \sin \omega t$$

Tenglamadan $t=0$ da hosil bo'ladi).

Shu maqsadda hosilani yozip olamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{di}{dt} = & -\delta e^{-\delta t}(C_1 \cos \omega_1 t + C_2 \sin \omega_1 t) + e^{-\delta t}(-C_1 \omega_1 \sin \omega_1 t + C_2 \omega_1 \cos \omega_1 t) \\ & + \frac{E}{Z^2}(X\omega \sin \omega t + R\omega \cos \omega t) \end{aligned}$$

Va $t=0$ qiymatni I va $\frac{di}{dt}$ ning ifodalariga qo'yamiz:

$$0 = C_1 - \frac{EX}{Z^2}, \text{ bu yerdan } C_1 = \frac{EX}{Z^2}; \quad 0 = -\delta C_1 + \omega_1 C_2 + \frac{ER\omega}{Z^2};$$

Bu yerdan

$$C_2 = \frac{1}{\omega_1} \left(\delta C_1 - \frac{ER\omega}{Z^2} \right) = -\frac{E}{Z^2 \omega_1} (R\omega - X\delta).$$

Qavsda turgan ifodani quyidagicha o'zgartiramiz:

$$\begin{aligned} R\omega - X\delta = R\omega - \frac{R}{2L} \left(L\omega - \frac{1}{C\omega} \right) &= R\omega - \frac{R\omega}{2} + \frac{\delta}{C\omega} = \frac{R\omega}{2} + \frac{\delta}{C\omega} = \\ &= \delta \left(L\omega + \frac{1}{C\omega} \right) = \delta X', \end{aligned}$$

Bu yerdan $L\omega + \frac{1}{C\omega} = X'$ deb belgilangan.

Shunday qilib,

$$i = \frac{E}{Z^2 \omega} e^{-\delta t} (X \omega_1 \cos \omega_1 t - X' \delta \sin \omega_1 t) - \frac{E}{Z^2} (X \cos \omega t - R \sin \omega t).$$

Belgilash kiritamiz: $\frac{X \omega_1}{\sqrt{X^2 \omega_1^2 + X'^2 \delta^2}} = \sin \gamma_1$, $\frac{X' \delta}{\sqrt{X^2 \omega_1^2 + X'^2 \delta^2}} = \cos \gamma_1$

yoki

$$X^2 \omega_1^2 + X'^2 \delta^2 = \frac{Z^2}{LC} \quad (4)$$

bo'lgani uchun $\frac{X \sqrt{LC} \omega_1}{Z} = \sin \gamma_1$, $\frac{X' \sqrt{LC} \delta}{Z} = \cos \gamma_1$.

(4) munosabat quyidagicha hosil bo'ladi. Quyidagiga egamiz:

$$L\omega = X + \frac{1}{C\omega}, \quad L\omega = X' - \frac{1}{C\omega},$$

Bu yerdan

$$X' = X + \frac{2}{C\omega} \quad \text{va} \quad X'^2 = X^2 + \frac{4}{C\omega} \left(X + \frac{1}{C\omega} \right).$$

Demak,

$$\begin{aligned} X^2 \omega_1^2 + X'^2 \delta^2 &= X^2 \left(\frac{1}{LC} - \delta^2 \right) + \left[X^2 + \frac{4}{C\omega} \left(X + \frac{1}{C\omega} \right) \right] \delta^2 \\ &= \frac{X^2}{LC} + \frac{4}{C\omega} \left(L\omega - \frac{1}{C\omega} + \frac{1}{C\omega} \right) \delta^2 = \\ &= \frac{X^2}{LC} + \frac{4LR^2}{C4L^2} = \frac{1}{LC} (X^2 + R^2) = \frac{Z^2}{LC}. \end{aligned}$$

Xuddi yuqoridagiga o'xshash belgilaymiz:

$$\frac{X}{\sqrt{X^2 + R^2}} = \sin \gamma_1, \quad R/\sqrt{X^2 + R^2} = \cos \gamma_1 \quad \text{yoki} \quad X/Z = \sin \gamma,$$

$R/Z = \cos \gamma$. Natijada quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$i = -\frac{E X^{-\delta t}}{Z \sqrt{LC} \omega_1} \sin(\omega_1 t - \gamma_1) + \frac{E}{Z} \sin(\omega t - \gamma),$$

Bu yerda $\operatorname{tg} \gamma_1 = \frac{X\omega}{X'\delta}$, $\operatorname{tg} \gamma = \frac{X}{R}$.

$\omega = \omega_1$ bo'lgan holda hususiy yechim $\bar{i} = t(A \cos \omega t + B \sin \omega t)$

Ko'rinishda izlash kerakligini eslatip o'taylik.

t ko'paytuvchining borligi tebranish amplitudasi cheksiz o'sishini ko'rsatadi; $\omega = \omega_1$ bo'lgan hol rezonansni bildiradi.

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